

MUSIC-BASED PROGRAM (MBP) FOR ENGLISH GRAMMAR SKILLS ENHANCEMENT OF TRIBAL LEARNERS

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Abstract

The study set out to develop and implement a Music-Based Program (MBP) to enhance the English grammar skills of tribal learners. The efficacy of this program was determined in association with written and oral grammar skills achievement. The experimental study used a convenient sampling strategy following a pre-test and post-test non-equivalent control group design. Data was collected using the English Grammar Skills Achievement Test and Reaction Scale. The study was conducted through two segments, each including four distinct data-gathering phases. Mean, Standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U-test, percentage, and intensity index were employed to analyze and scrutinize the data quantitatively. The MBP significantly enhanced the achievement of grammar skills in the experimental class IX group. The use of Music-Based Programs to teach grammar to tribal learners is also in line with the NEP-2020, which highlights music and art-integrated learning. The study's promising results have far-reaching implications for using music as a pedagogical tool in English language teaching and learning.

Keywords: Music-Based Program (MBP), Enhancement, English Grammar Skills, Tribal Learners.

INTRODUCTION

English language learning is a compulsory component of school education, and grammar skill enhancement is the foundation of learning any foreign/ second language to hone language skills. For effective communication, both written and spoken grammar skills are crucial.

Numerous studies abroad demonstrate that English grammar teaching with music is

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pedagogically and linguistically sound. Rap/Hip-Hop music is used to teach vocabulary, grammar, discourse, and other skills in English language teaching since teaching English has emerged as a universal compulsory activity in formal education due to its global need. Several researchers have used music, including grammar, as a language teaching and learning resource. Engh (2012), Weinstein (2006), and Beth (2014) all used rap and pop music to express themselves and teach grammar and speech in the English language. 'Rapping' is a sample curriculum-based program designed by Beth Segal to teach English language speech and grammar in 2014. Carolyn Graham (1992) found Jazz Chants and created a program based on them to use in ESL classroom teaching as a music technique for teaching English grammar. T. Murphey (1992) made the discourse of pop songs to teach English. Various studies (Maley, 1997; Eken, 1996; Gaston, 1968; Geoff, 2003) have been conducted in different countries on using songs as an authentic teaching resource in language teaching and learning, including grammar. According to Paquette and Rieg (2008), fluency in grammar, reading, and writing is crucial in language learning. Music can contribute to students improving their writing and other literacy skills, including grammar. Hence, in a school setting, songs can aid in teaching not only sounds, rhythm, and stress but also polite formulae, sentence structures, vocabulary, and syntax (Richards, 1969). Since grammar instruction is integral to language instruction in India, it can be a useful pedagogical tool for tribal students to improve their English grammar skills. Music is deeply rooted in tribal life and culture. The value of music in language learning for tribals cannot be undermined. Music is the essence of indigenous people's culture. The cultural traditions of the country's diverse tribal regions reflect the fantastic range of India's regional tribal folk music. Each tribal county has its diverse aesthetic of music culture (Vidyardhi & Rai, 1985). Pedagogical techniques, like teaching English grammar through music, can make language education enjoyable for tribal students. National Education Policy 2020 suggests integrating tribal art and music into pedagogical techniques for tribal-specific learners. The study aimed to develop an MBP and to use MBP to enhance the English grammar skills of tribal learners, to determine the effectiveness of the MBP in terms of achievement in English grammar skills, and to measure the reaction of the students towards the MBP used in teaching English grammar.

THE MBP: SYSTEMATIZATION

The music-based program was developed in an organized system. The MBP was designed to hone tribal learners' grammar skills at the secondary level during the regular class duration of

English Classes. The secondary-level intellectual capabilities of tribal learners were taken into consideration. The lack of achievement in grammar skills among tribal learners denotes the necessity of enhancing grammar skills. The class-time constrictions of the grammar class hour, the environment of teaching and learning, and the sociocultural ethnic constraints of the tribal students, etc., were considered in the development of the program.

PLAN AND PROCEDURE OF THE STUDY

The current research was split into two sections.

SEGMENT I: MBP DEVELOPMENT

Segment I comprised the four stages for developing the MBP developed by the researcher.

Step I: Identification of Grammar Content

This step analyzed the grammar content to finalize the grammar topics. The textbook analysis highlighted that the English textbook of the secondary section comprises prose, poetry, and grammar categories. All the grammar categories are explained thoroughly, along with the exercises, below each textbook unit.

Step II: Preparation of Grammar Songs for Teaching Through MBP

The MBP was developed based on the grammar content analysis of the English textbook of class IX. The verses were written and set to the tribal tunes to use as an MBP in the form of 'Grammar Songs' for grammar teaching. It comprised grammar rules and their usage. The books, 'Grammar Skills book series (Scholastic Asia, 2017) and Oxford Primary English Grammar Skills series (Oxford et al.,2014), High School English Grammar & Composition (Wren & Martin,1999), etc., were referred to along with web links, for writing the grammar songs.

Step III: Selection of Grammar Instructional Inputs: Activities

Various English songs were selected for the activities according to their grammar suitability. Activities were planned to give practice for better learning of the grammar content. The researcher employed grammar songs accompanied by karaoke and English song-based activities in terms of the MBP to teach English Grammar in the classroom. Activities-based English songs of different music genres were utilized.

Step IV: Lesson Plan Format

The researcher Prepared a detailed lesson plan comprising all the grammar topics and subtopics. Sixty-four lesson plan sessions were prepared to teach grammar through the MBP. Each week, two consecutive sessions were arranged for grammar teaching. General Formatting

of the grammar lesson plan comprised the objectives (General and specific), Procedure, Evaluation, etc. Each session follows the lesson plan's identical structure, which comprises commencement with general objectives and concluding with learning results. Following the session's objectives, songs and music embedded in the MBP were used as instructional inputs. Explanations with examples of the grammar category, drills, practices, and exercises with activity inputs for each grammar topic were included in the lesson plan—English Song-based activities.

SEGMENT II.: METHODOLOGY

The proposed study was experimental in nature, using a quasi-experimental design. It used a pre-test and post-test non-equivalent control group design. All IX standard students studying English in Grant-in-Aid Marathi Medium Schools affiliated with the Maharashtra State Secondary and Higher Secondary Education Board (MSHSEB) constituted the study population. The sample was selected using a convenient sampling technique. The experimental and control groups were equalized through the pretest achievement scores of English grammar tests. After matching the groups, these equivalent groups of 46 learners from each were considered the final sample for the study.

MATERIALS

Data collection for the research investigation was accomplished using the following research tools.

English Grammar Skills Achievement Test:

English grammar skills achievement tests worth 100 marks were prepared by comprising 1) written grammar skill achievement Tests of 50 Marks and 2) oral grammar skill achievement tests of 50 Marks.

Reaction Scale:

The researcher developed a self-made reaction scale to measure the students' reactions to the MBP used for teaching English grammar. The researcher administered the five-point Likert-type reaction scale, which has 25 statements, to the experimental group of students.

PROCEDURE

The research investigation was accomplished through the following four phases.

Phase 1. Development of the (MBP) MBP

Based on the grammar content analysis of the English textbook of class IX, the researcher developed the MBP. The researcher wrote the verses and set them to the tune to use them as the MBP for grammar teaching. The grammar rules and usage verses were prepared as a MBP for English grammar teaching.

Phase 2: Pre-Test

It is a pre-test phase in which a 100-mark Pre-Test, consisting of 1) the written grammar skill achievement tests of 50 marks and the oral grammar skill achievement Tests of 50 Marks, was administered to both the experimental and control groups.

Phase 3: Implementation of the MBP

At this phase, the intervention of the MBP, which the investigator developed to teach grammar in class IX of tribal Ashram school learners to enhance their grammar skills through music for an academic year. The control group was taught conventionally. The lesson plans on all the prescribed grammar topics of class IX English subject were prepared, and the MBP was integrated into the lesson plans. During teaching, the 'Grammar Songs' were sung accompanied by Karaoke. The Audio-videos of English, lyrical video songs, Song lyrics-activity worksheets, grammar topic PowerPoint presentations, grammar songs' sheets, English songs-based activity sheets, worksheets, and grammar handouts of various topics were used as the resources for the effective implementation of the MBP.

Phase 4: Post-Test

In the study's post-test phase, 100-mark Grammar Skills Achievement Tests were conducted. The written grammar skill achievement tests of 50 marks and the oral grammar skill achievement tests of 50, as a post-test, were administered to both the groups, i.e., experimental and control groups. The Post-test of 50 marks in both terms consisted of 25 marks for the written grammar skill achievement test and 25 for the oral grammar skill achievement test each term. The post-tests were given to class IX tribal learners to measure the achievement in English grammar skills in experimental and control groups. A Likert-type reaction scale of 25 statements was also administered to the experimental group to measure their reaction toward teaching English grammar through the MBP.

DATA ANALYSIS: INTERPRETATION

The data was computed, and the means of the students' post-test scores were considered for the experimental and control groups. The analyses and interpretations of the results are presented in tables.

Table No. 1.1 Mean, Standard Deviation, And Standard Error of Mean of Experimental Group and Control Group for Achievement of Grammar Skills in English Language.

Achievement Of Grammar Skills in English Language	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error of Mean
Experimental Group	46	60.1957	6.39312	.94261
Control Group	46	25.3261	6.57623	.96961

Graphical Representation of the Table No. 1-1

From Table 1.1 and the graphical presentation, it was detected that the mean achievement score for grammar skills tests in the English language of the experimental group students was 60.19. In contrast, the mean achievement score of the control group students was 25.32. It was also seen that the standard deviation of the experimental group was 6.39 from the scores for achievement of grammar skills in the English language, whereas 6.57 was the Standard deviation for the control group from the scores for achievement of grammar skills in the English language. The standard error of the mean for the experimental group was 0.94, whereas it was 0.97 for the control group. The comparison of the means demonstrated that the mean achievement score of the experimental group was significantly more significant than the mean achievement score of the study's control group. The intervention of the MBP in teaching grammar to enhance English grammar skills achievement was the cause of the experimental group's mean score in the achievement of grammar skills being more significant than that of the control group. To ascertain whether the variance in the mean was by chance or significant as well as to test the null hypothesis, i.e., **Ho, "There will be no significant difference**

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between the mean post-test scores of students of the control and experimental group of class IX in the achievement of grammar skills in the English language.” The test, called ‘The Mann-Whitney U test,’ was employed as the convenience sampling method used by the researcher. Table no. 1.2, mentioned below, demonstrates the encapsulation of the test followed by an interpretation.

Table 1.2: Summary: The Mann-Whitney U-Test for the Achievement of Grammar Skills in English Language for Both Experimental Control Groups’ Students with the Number of Samples, Sum of Ranks, U-Value, Z-Value, and Probability

Students	N	Sum Of Ranks	U-Value	Z- Value	Probability(P)
Experimental Group	46	3197.00	000.000	-8.266	0.000
Control Group	46	1081.00			

From the table no. 1.2, it was notified clearly that the experimental group had the sum of the ranks of 3197, whereas the control group students had the sum of the ranks of 1081 in achieving grammar skills in the English language, with 46 students in each group. In the present study, the U-value was found to be 0.00, and the Z-value was found to be -8.266. According to Siegel's 1956 Table A, for Normal probability, under the null hypothesis (H_0) of z , for $z \leq -8.266$, the two-tailed probability in the present study was found to be 0.00, which was found to be lesser than our determined $\alpha = 0.01$. Therefore, in the current research study, the null hypothesis, i.e., “There will be no significant difference between the mean post-test scores of students of the control and experimental group of class IX in the achievement of grammar skills in the English language.” was rejected. Hence, it was clear that the experimental and the control group students contrasted significantly on account of the achievement of grammar skills in the English language. From Table 1.2, it was also clear that the mean scores of the experimental group were more significant than the mean scores of the control group, which could be attributed to the intervention of an MBP in the enhanced achievement of grammar skills in the English language. As a result, it can be proclaimed that the enhancement of the tribal students' English grammar skills in the experimental group was statistically more significant than the enhancement of their grammar skills in the control group. This outcome of the present research study was due to the intervention of the MBP.

STUDY RESULTS: MAJOR FINDINGS

The study's significant findings revealed that the Music-Based Program was effective in relation to achievement in written and oral grammar skills. The achievement of grammar skills significantly differed in the experimental and control groups of class IX students. The grammar skills were found to be higher in the experimental group. Students' reactions were favorable toward the MBP used to enhance grammar skills through music. The overall intensity index was 4.76.

DISCUSSION:

The present study's findings revealed that the difference was significant in the achievement of grammar skills in the students of the experimental group of class IX. The grammar teaching through the MBP for the experimental group of tribal learners effectively enhanced the present study's written and oral grammar skills. The learners' reaction was found to be favorable towards the MBP, which was developed and intervened for grammar teaching to enhance their grammar skills through music. The difference found was significantly higher in terms of the achievement of grammar skills of the tribal learners of the experimental group than that of the control group of learners of class IX. The intervention of the MBP effectively enhanced tribal students' grammar skills at the secondary level.

During the study, the researcher noticed that the students thoroughly enjoyed the grammar teaching through the MBP for the 64 sessions due to its melody. It was also clearly noticed that the tribal tunes of the grammar songs, composed and sung by the researcher, were familiar to them, which made their learning proactive with lots of fun. Using English song-based activities gave different learning experiences for enhancing written and oral grammar skills. The set of ten grammar songs composed and sung by the researcher was helpful for the learners to understand the grammar content easily. It made learning grammar rules for the topics and their use in written and spoken grammar skills easy and sustainable for tribal learners. This is consistent with the findings of Sebastian's (2014) study that the technique of song-based grammar teaching in the classroom can help learners retain the knowledge of grammatical categories more efficiently and with greater enjoyment than through the traditional methods of teaching.

The observations obtained during various activities showed that the pupils found the grammar lessons engaging, entertaining, and interesting because of the music element that worked as a pedagogical tool. This is consistent with the study of Hashim and Rahman (2010), whose

conclusions demonstrated the value of song-based activities for reinforcing SVA learning and creating a joyful classroom environment. The grammar songs were enjoyed and recited willingly with lots of excitement and happiness during classroom learning by the students. Learners enjoyed the grammar songs and found it very easy to thoroughly comprehend the grammar skills content knowledge, which they demonstrated in written and spoken English communication skills. The study found a significant difference in the achievement of English grammar skills at the secondary level. This finding is aligned with Sebastian's study (2014), in which considerable achievement was found in grammatical awareness through songs at the high school level. Her study's findings have confirmed that the novel teaching module based on the medium of music helps to sustain learning and, therefore, improves the students' knowledge of grammar. Her study highlighted the effectiveness of teaching grammar using music as a novel teaching module. The students' favorable reaction to all the statements of the reaction scales proved the utility and effectiveness of the MBP. The overwhelming enthusiasm, interest, and engagement during the MBP-oriented activities proved its educational and pedagogical significance. It was demonstrated during the classroom activities and reflected in their scores on achievement tests and reactions scale. This is also consistent with the study by Bhamare (2017), wherein songs, film segments, and videos, as authentic materials, proved to be very effective supportive materials for language teaching and learning. It was also noted in the same study that language learning happened in a light environment rather than in a dry academic one. The learners enjoy learning and get motivated when exposed to a non-academic environment where authentic materials like songs, films, and videos support language learning. The researcher also noticed that integrating 'Grammar-Songs' and English songs of different genres in the MBP made the grammar teaching-learning procedure appealing. However, in the traditional English grammar class, the pupils were rarely allowed to utilize music as a resource. The use of rap, pop, hip-hop, and jazz chants music was found to be consistent in the studies conducted by T. Murphey (1992), Engh (2012), Weinstein (2006), and Beth (2014) to teach grammar and speech in the English language. T. Murphey (1992) made the discourse of pop songs to teach English. 'Rapping' is a sample curriculum-based program designed by Beth to teach English language speech and grammar in 2014. According to Weinstein (2006), hip-hop and rap have a voice in a society that embodies a political discourse that enriches language classes. Rap/Hip-hop music is universally used in teaching English since there is a global demand for it, and it has become a universally compulsory subject in formal education in many

countries. Several researchers have used music, including grammar, as a language teaching and learning resource. Graham (1992) found jazz chants and created a program based on them to use in ESL classroom teaching as a music technique for teaching English grammar.

The current study was an effort to teach grammar through music, which was a part of the MBP, to the tribal learners at the secondary level in Maharashtra state, as music is found to be deep-rooted in the tribal culture. Using MBPs to teach grammar to tribal learners aligns with the NEP -2020, highlighting the art & music integrated learning. According to the new education policy, tribal art, and music must be an innovative pedagogical tool for such tribal-specific learners. The successful results of such programs will open the door for policymakers, higher authorities, and educators in schools to make a cognizant, purposeful, and systematic effort to enhance the English grammar skills of learners through the MBP. Therefore, it was found that various musical tunes, grammar songs, and English song-based activities used in the Music-Based Program made teaching grammar a musical fun. The significant enhancement of grammar skills of the tribal learners through music at the secondary level has proven to be educationally sound. Additionally, the favorable reaction of the learners towards the MBP in teaching and learning English grammar at the secondary level has proven the program's effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, the researcher's self-made Music-Based Program (MBP) has proven effective in enhancing students' written and oral grammar skill achievement. Additionally, the favorable reactions of the tribal learners towards the MBP of teaching grammar showed that the program was effective. The successful results of the study have paved the way for the implications. Firstly, the findings of the study have implications for the curriculum developers. Different pedagogical tools like music for teaching grammar content can be included in the curriculum. School teachers can utilize Music-Based Programs for English grammar content at the various levels of school education. Secondly, the pedagogical tool of teaching through music has implications for policymakers responsible for developing teacher education curricula with a focus on pedagogy courses at all stages of education. Thirdly, Institutional Heads and Educational Administrators can design in-service training programs for school teachers and stakeholders to implement music as the pedagogical tool for teaching English grammar.

REFERENCES

- Beth, S. (2014). *Teaching English as a second language through rap music: A curriculum for secondary school students*. Master's Theses. University of San Francisco 104. <https://repository.usfca.edu/thes/104/>
- Bhamare, Y. (2017). *The teaching of language skills through songs, film segments, and video clips*. An unpublished thesis submitted to the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences Symbiosis International University at The Symbiosis International University.
- Eken, D. K. (1996). *Ideas For Using Pop Songs in The English Language Classroom*. *English Teaching Forum* 34: pp. 234–41.
- Engh, D. (2012). *Why use music in English language learning? A survey of the literature*. *English language teaching*. 6(2), 113–127. doi 10.5539/elt.V6n2p13 "English-language learners." Edweek.org. Published: August 4, 2004, Updated June 16, 2014. <http://www.edweek.org/ew/issues/english-language-learners/>
- Gaston, E.T. (1968). *Music in Therapy*. New York: Macmillan.
- Geoff, P.S. (2003). *Music And Mondegreens: Extracting Meaning from Noise*. *ELT Journal* 57/2: 113-121
- Graham, C. (1992). *Singing, changing, telling tales: Arts in the language classroom*. Prentice-Hall Regents.
- Graham, C. (1994). *Mother Goose Jazz Chants*. Oxford University Press.
- Grammar Skills (2017) Book series (1-7) published by Scholastic Asia.
- Hashim, A.B., and S.B.A. Rahman (2010). *Using songs to reinforce the learning of Subject-Verb Agreement*. University of Teknologi Malaysia. 1-5. <http://eprints.utm.musingsongstoreinforcethelearning.pdf>.
- Li, X., & Brand, M. (2009). *Effectiveness of music on vocabulary acquisition, language usage, and meaning for mainland Chinese ESL learners*. *Contributions to Music Education*, 36(1), 7383.
- Lozanov, G. (1978). *Suggestology and suggestopedia – Theory and practice*. United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization
- Maley, A. (1997). *Poetry and Song as Effective Language-learning Activities*. In Wigla M. R. *Interactive Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Pp. 93–109.
- Murphey, T. (1992). *The discourse of pop songs*. *TESOL Quarterly* 26.4: pp. 770–774.
- Murphey, T. & Maley A. (1992). *Music & Song: Oxford English resource books for teachers*. Oxford University Press; Illustrated edition
- NEP. (2020) *New Education Policy*. [NEP_Final_English_0.pdf](https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf)
- Oxford Primary English Grammar Skills series (2014) Oxford University Press
- Paquette, Kelli R., and Rieg Sue A. (2008). "Using Music to Support the Literacy Development of Young English Language Learners." *Early Childhood Education Journal* 36.3 227-32.
- Richards, J. (1969). *Songs in language learning*. *TESOL Quarterly*, 3(2), 161–174.
- Sebastian, E. (2014). *Developing grammatical awareness through songs to teach grammar to the high school students of Palakkad district*. An unpublished thesis was submitted to the Research and Development Centre at Bharathiar University.
- Vidyatrthi, L. P & Rai B. K. (a1985). *The Tribal Culture of India*. 2018th edition. Concept Publishing Company Pvt. Ltd.
- Weinstein, S. (2006). *A love for the thing: The pleasures of rap as a literate practice*. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 50(4), 270-281. doi:10.1598/JAAL.50.4.3
- Wren. P. C. and H. Martin. (1999): *High school English grammar and composition*. S. Chanda and Company Ltd.